

THEROS

An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain

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D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version)

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Executive Summary

Communication, dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities are essential to assure the success of a project as ambitious and visionary as THEROS. Funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, the aim of THEROS is to implement an integrated toolbox being capable to modernise the process of verifying organic and geographical indications food products. THEROS aims to prevent adulterations and non-compliances, through the use of various technological innovations and data sources, while demonstrating enhanced security, transparency and interoperability in the quality labelled food supply chain.

This document, designated as D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version), is considered a dynamic document linked to Task 6.1 "Dissemination & communication" and Task 6.3 "THEROS Ground-Breakers Advisory Board", but also to Task 6.2 "Liaison with EU bodies and other relevant research activities & projects within EU (including projects funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-10, HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-11 and HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-17 call-topics) and beyond & THEROS knowledge base", within Work Package WP6 "THEROS high impact creation and sustainability".

This document's primary purpose is to provide a thorough summary of the scientific, communication, and dissemination efforts made by THEROS consortium partners between the commencement of the project and M24 (December 2024). The main objective of these efforts is to increase awareness and outreach among different target groups about THEROS findings, outputs, and technical work carried out over the project's two-year length.

More specifically, the report provides quantitative information on the status of THEROS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and methods, scientific activities conducted, participation in prominent conferences and events, as well as details on clustering and networking activities.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DoA	Description of Action
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
D1.1	Deliverable number 1 belonging to WP 1
GA	Grant Agreement
GI	Geographical Indication
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
Mx	Month x
MS	Microsoft
ORE	Open Research Europe
PMs	Person Months
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
RnD	Research and Development
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The current deliverable, *D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version)*, is the first update of D6.1 "THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (initial version)", which constitutes a key reference document for all the communication, dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities to be implemented within WP6 of THEROS project and it is intended as a living document through the project's lifetime.

This deliverable has been prepared and delivered by SEAB, as lead beneficiary of the Work Package 6 'THEROS high impact creation and sustainability', towards recording the contributions from all THEROS project partners.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document contains all communication, dissemination, scientific and activities performed, attended, organised, and conducted from the beginning of the project until M24 (December 2024) by THEROS consortium partners.

1.2 Intended readership

D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version) is a public deliverable and constitutes a very useful follow-up, addressed not only to the consortium members, but also to any interested reader (i.e., Public (PU) dissemination level).

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC), Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the THEROS project as a useful update and assessment to THEROS communication, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities.

Nevertheless, special effort and focus has been, also, given on making this report a stand-alone comprehensible document for the general public.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 1 introduces the purpose of the document, the intended readership and the document structure.

Section 2 provides a status description of THEROS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and means.

Section 3 presents the scientific activities that have been conducted by M24.

Section 4 summarises THEROS attendance and participation in related events, conferences, seminars, workshops, and exhibitions, by M24.

Section 5 describes the performed clustering and networking activities during the first two years of the project.

Section 6 highlights the interaction with the THEROS Advisory Board.

Section 7 analyses the status of the evaluation and monitoring processes of the THEROS communication and dissemination activities during the first two years of the project duration.

Finally, section 8 summarizes the concluding remarks of D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version).

2. THEROS Communication Kit (Channels, Tools & Means)

Since the project's commencement, a wide range of channels, tools, and means have been created, implemented, and actively used to spread information about THEROS, increase awareness, and engage the targeted audiences effectively. These efforts have been tailored to meet the specific needs and characteristics of each audience group. The following summary outlines the communication channels, tools, and means that have been established for sharing information, results, outcomes, and progress within the THEROS project, while also providing an update on their status and development over the first two years of the project duration.

2.1 *Online channels*

THEROS project's online channels include the project's website and the social media accounts.

2.1.1 Project website

THEROS website serves as the primary foundation for the project's communication and dissemination activities. It functions as a central hub for various users and stakeholders, providing clear and up to date information about the project's goals, key areas, pilot demonstrations, consortium members, outcomes, and related material and initiatives. The related material includes public deliverables, open-access publications, newsletters, dissemination materials, and news updates. Officially launched on M01 (January 2023) and became fully functional, in its current view (Figure 1), on M03 (March 2023), the website features multiple sections, such as Home, About, Consortium, Material Hub, Cluster info and News & Events, and can be accessed at <https://theros-project.eu/>.

Figure 1 Indicative screenshot of THEROS website-main page

Since M23 (November 2024), THEROS website has been updated with an additional page (Figure 2) in the main navigation bar, dedicated to the Cluster of sister and related projects. This page offers a brief overview of each project, including links to their respective websites, and provides details on the collaborative activities carried out within the cluster projects.

Figure 2 Our Cluster page on THEROS's website

According to THEROS website analytics shown in Figure 3, the total number of users has reached 2.7k users¹, within the first 24 months of the project, while the website views has reached 8.7k views, within the same period. Also, the average session duration² is approximately 01:00 min and the total number of sessions, within the recorded period, is 137.846 sessions.

Figure 3 THEROS website analytics

¹ According to Google Analytics [1], "Total users" is the total number of people who visited THEROS site in a specified date range

² A session in Google Analytics is a group of interactions recorded when a user visits the website within a given period.

2.1.2 Social Media accounts

Since the project's launch in M01 (January 2023), THEROS has actively maintained three social media accounts on Twitter/X, LinkedIn, and YouTube to boost the dissemination of project results and encourage engagement. SEAB has been responsible for setting up and managing these accounts, ensuring they are well-integrated with the project website. The visibility and effectiveness of these accounts are regularly monitored through both quantitative metrics from platform analytics and qualitative assessments of user feedback and comments. Additionally, content related to partner activities has further enhanced THEROS presence on social media.

2.1.2.1 Twitter/X account

THEROS Twitter/X account (@THEROS_project) acts as a platform for sharing the latest project updates, including regular posts and photos from THEROS partners. It highlights activities such as meetings, workshops, and events, and also retweets relevant content from similar initiatives and projects. Additionally, all THEROS partners help increase the visibility of this channel by linking it to their own accounts and providing SEAB with pertinent content and updates on their achievements. By M24, THEROS Twitter/X account had gained 97 followers. The account can be accessed at https://x.com/THEROS_project, and two referenced posts can be shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4 Twitter/X post from THEROS account

Figure 5 Twitter/X post from THEROS account

2.1.2.2 LinkedIn account

THEROS LinkedIn account (@THEROS_project) was created to share relevant content, engage with prominent groups, and communicate the project's insights, vision, concept, and progress. By M24, the account had accumulated 286 followers. Analytics show (Figure 6) that over the past 12 months (December 2023–December 2024), the account generated around 12k organic impressions and 513 reactions. THEROS LinkedIn page can be accessed at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/theros-project/?viewAsMember=true>.

Figure 6 Organic impressions over the last 12 months (December 2023–December 2024)

2.1.2.3 YouTube account

THEROS project also operates a YouTube channel (Figure 7) aimed at sharing videos that highlight the project's achievements as part of its communication and dissemination strategy. This platform is a key resource for showcasing general project videos and pilot demos - when available- and other audiovisual materials e.g. partner's videos. THEROS YouTube account can be accessed at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdXfA8j2Qi2fg-yMh7hUobg>.

Figure 7 THEROS YouTube Channel

By M24, the THEROS YouTube channel has uploaded 15 videos. According to page analytics (Figure 8), have accumulated a total of 877 views, with an average viewing time of 2.5 minutes.

Content	Duration	Publication date	Views ↓	Average viewing time	Average view rate
<input type="checkbox"/> Total			877	2:30	59.4%

Figure 8 YouTube Analytics

2.2 Dissemination Tools

The dissemination tools for THEROS, available in both print and digital formats, are aligned with the project's overall communication strategy to ensure its objectives are achieved and target audiences are effectively engaged. These materials are designed in accordance with THEROS brand identity and the European Commission's communication guidelines [2]. The dissemination kit includes the project's fact sheet, general presentation, brochure, poster, roll-up banner, the upcoming official project video, and short video trials. All these materials are in detail described within D6.1: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (initial version).

All the updated by the end of the project will be thoroughly reported within D6.3 "THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version)", due in M36.

2.3 Communication Means

2.3.1 THEROS e-newsletters

THEROS website provides visitors with the opportunity to subscribe to a regular newsletter (Figure 9), serving as an effective electronic channel for distributing project updates, findings, activities, and upcoming events. These e-newsletters are sent via email to subscribers and are also available in digital format on the THEROS website under the Material Hub, within the Newsletter section.

In addition, related posts on THEROS social media platforms, such as Twitter/X and LinkedIn, help expand their reach. By M24, the newsletter list had 70 subscribers. The newsletter content highlights the project's ongoing progress and aims to keep audiences and stakeholders informed about its key outcomes and results.

Figure 9 THEROS e-newsletter subscription functionality

Three e-newsletters have already been launched during the first 24 months of the project, and they are presented in <https://theros-project.eu/newsletters/> (and Figure 10) below:

Table 1 THEROS e-newsletters

THEROS e-newsletters
THEROS 1 st e-newsletter https://mailchi.mp/741f5373ae01/theros-e-newsletter-issue-1?e=9751e01de5

<p>THEROS 2nd e-newsletter https://mailchi.mp/519812cbf120/theros-e-newsletter-issue-12677093</p>
<p>THEROS 3rd e-newsletter https://mailchi.mp/8c5e2f04a74c/theros-e-newsletter-third-issue</p>

Figure 10 Indicative screenshots from THEROS three e-newsletters

2.3.2 THEROS partners interview series

THEROS Communication Campaign was initiated as a discussion among partners within the first project year and released by the end of the first year (M12). The campaign was launched under the title "Meet THEROS Team". Each partner was asked to prepare a short video 2-3 min to explain its role within THEROS as well as to communicate its main results and achievements.

By M24, 12 out of 17 videos (Figure 11) were made available both on THEROS YouTube channels, as well as through THEROS website, in the material hub, under audiovisual material section. Videos are also disseminating through THEROS's LinkedIn and Twitter/X accounts, as well as featured in the THEROS newsletter.

The campaign is expected to be concluded by February 2025, with the release of the last five videos.

Figure 11 THEROS Campaign videos released (by M24)

2.3.3 THEROS press activities

Press releases play a crucial role in highlighting the achievements and progress of the project partners. Since the start of the project, THEROS team has published multiple press releases, as outlined in Table 2. These press materials are available on THEROS website in the Material Hub, within the Media Centre section, ensuring wide visibility and effective distribution of the project's key milestones.

Table 2 THEROS press activities between M01-M24

Type of activity	Title of publication	Date	Involved partners	Press Clippings (url)
Kick-off website release	THEROS kick-off meeting in Athens	27/02/2023	SEAB	https://seability.eu/2023/02/27/theros-kick-off-meeting-in-athens/
Kick-off press release	THEROS kick-off meeting	05/03/2023	ELGO	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/chrysoula-tassou-49652437_food-project-foodauthenticity-activity-7038201295526051840-nTyG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

				https://www.facebook.com/100069375692504/posts/pfbid02rKm4Q7p6nCg8vJ2QB1cu4JkS4XMjTCBFYzFQfQp9hCPwg7m4mbkhFhQJqoR172tbl/?app=fbl
Kick-off press release	Συμμετοχή του BIOHELLAS στο Ευρωπαϊκό Πρόγραμμα «THEROS»	09/03/2023	BIOHELLAS	https://bio-hellas.gr/symmetochi-toy-biohellas-sto-eyropaiko-programma-theros/
		10/03/2023		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/biohellas-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B9%CE%BD%CF%83%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%8D%CF%84%CE%BF-%CF%80%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%80%CE%BF%CF%AF%CE%B7%CF%83%CE%B7%CF%82-%CE%B2%CE%B9%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8E%CE%BD-%CF%80%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%8A%CF%8C%CE%BD%CF%84%CF%89%CE%BD-activity-7039900831227207680-yWx9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
		11/03/2023		https://www.facebook.com/BioHellasOfficial/
Kick-off press release	The Horizon Europe THEROS Project Kicks Off	28/02/2023	eBOS	https://ebos.com.cy/the-horizon-europe-theros-project-kicks-off/ https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=717338346648112&set=a.579234347125180
Announcement of THEROS project	Transparency and trust in organic food supply chain & GI products	24/04/2023	OCS	https://organica.rs/en/about-us/projects/
Press article for the participation in the International Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad	Business meetings of organic producers at the International Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad (Poslovni susreti organskih proizvođača na Međunarodnom	22/05/2024	OCS	https://vojvodinauzivo.rs/polslojni-susreti-organskih-proizvodjaca-na-medjunarodnom-poljoprivrednom-sajmu-u-novom-sadu/

	poljoprivrednom sajmu u Novom Sadu)			
	Meeting of organic producers at the Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad (Сусрет органских произвођача на Пољопривредном сајму у Новом Саду)	22/05/2024	OCS, Univerexpo rt DOO	https://www.rtv.rs/sr_ci/vojvodina/novi-sad/susret-organskih-proizvodjaca-na-poljoprivrednom-sajmu-u-novom-sadu_1541917.html
Press release on THEROS workshop as part of Země Živitelka agricultural exhibition	Workshop Venkov pod palbou dat – prezentace ke stažení	03/09/2024	WIRELESSINFO	https://www.wirelessinfo.cz/2024/09/03/workshop-venkov-pod-palbou-dat-prezentace-ke-stazeni/
Press article in the magazine 'Rutas Pesqueras'	Kiwa España colabora en el Proyecto europeo THEROS junto con el Consello Regulador DOP Mexillón de Galicia	September 2024	KIWA & MEXILLON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7240309490955304961
Press article in the agrosmart.net	"Samo je jedan Futoški kupus, oznaka geografskog porekla garantuje kvalitet	November 2024	OCS	https://agrosmart.net/2024/11/20/samo-je-jedan-futoski-kupus-oznaka-geografskog-porekla-garantuje-kvalitet/

3. THEROS scientific activities

3.1 Conducted activities

THEROS team is actively producing scientific publications and other contributions to technical literature and high-impact journals to share the project's progress and research findings with the academic community.

These publications aim to advance scientific knowledge by disseminating both empirical and theoretical work developed within the project. All scientific publications comply with the European Commission's Open Access regulations and guidelines [3], ensuring Open Access in line with the GA guidelines outlined in Annex 5, Article 17. This includes supporting both self-archiving ('Green' Open Access) and Open Access publishing ('Gold' Open Access) for publications and their metadata. Access will be provided to all interested stakeholders, primarily through THEROS public platforms (THEROS website) and/or EU-supported Open Access services, such as Open Research Europe (ORE), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and OpenAIRE. These services will assist THEROS partners in addressing challenges related to open access policies, including publisher embargo periods.

Since the project's start, THEROS has focused on producing relevant scientific content based on its achievements, reinforcing the project's visibility within the academic community. Additionally, THEROS maintains a list of targeted scientific journals to guide partners in submitting their research papers, as detailed in Annex 2 of Deliverable D6.1.

Table 3, below, provides a comprehensive overview of the scientific activities completed by the 24-month mark of the project.

Table 3 THEROS scientific activities M01-M24

Title	Authors	Event /Journal	Publication date/publisher	DOI/URL	Website announcement
An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain – THEROS project	David Kocman, Raghuraj Singh Chouhan, Jure Ftičar & THEROS consortium	2nd ISO-FOOD Symposium	April 2023	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/ISOFood_symposium_poster.pdf	https://theros-project.eu/iso-food-24-26-04-2023/
An integrated toolbox for improved	Dimitra Tsiakou, Elena Krikigianni,	FOODTECH congress	October 2024	https://theros-project.eu/wp	https://theros-project.eu/foodtech-

verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain – THEROS project	Svetlana Vitomirović			https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/e-ABSTRACT-BOOK-Foodtech2024-compressed.pdf	https://theros-project.eu/16-10-2024/
Towards dynamic digital product passport: the approach for food sector	L. Lekawska-Andrinopoulou, D. Tsiakou, K. Chatziioanou, G. Tsimiklis and A. Amditis	5th International Conference on Environmental Design and Health, ICED2024	October 2024	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/ICED203.pdf	https://theros-project.eu/5th-international-conference-on-environmental-design-and-health-iced2024-18-20-10-2024/
Real-Time Detection of Turmeric Adulteration with Metanil Yellow using a Miniaturized NIR Sensor and AI techniques	Dimitra Xenitopoulou, Nikolaos L. Tsakiridis, Achilleas Panagiotis Zalidis, Eleni Kalopesa, George C. Zalidis	38th EFFoST International Conference 2024	November 2024	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/EFFOST1.pdf	https://theros-project.eu/38th-effost-international-conference-202412-14-11-2024/

3.2 Upcoming scientific activities

Concerning the upcoming scientific activities, as part of THEROS project, AuTH team envisages the preparation and submission of two journal articles, as of below:

The first, provisionally titled "*Synergistic Use of Portable NIR Spectroscopy and Remote Sensing for Environmental Monitoring*", is expected to be submitted to the journal *Sensors*.

The second article, provisionally titled "*On-Site Detection of Talcum Powder Adulteration in Wheat Flour Using MEMS-Based NIR Spectroscopy: A Rapid and Efficient Analytical Approach*", is expected to be published in the *Journal of Food Measurement and Characterization*.

In addition, the rest of THEROS team's efforts will ensure that key results are disseminated through prominent journals, facilitating knowledge transfer and promoting the adoption of the technologies developed within the project. All updates will be thoroughly reported in D6.3 "THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version)", due on M36.

4. THEROS participation in Events & Conferences

THEROS actively engages in various events and conferences to showcase the project's progress, share key findings, and foster collaboration with stakeholders from academia, industry, and research institutions. These events provide valuable opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and the dissemination of THEROS's innovations. The following sections highlight the project's involvement in such events.

4.1 Conference events

The following Table 4 summarises THEROS attendance in related conferences during the first two years of the project duration.

Table 4 THEROS attended conferences between M01-M24

Date	Event	Location	Title of presentation	Involved partners	Description (if available)/url
24-26.04.2023	2nd ISO-FOOD Symposium	Portorož, Slovenia	An Integrated Toolbox for Improved Verification and Prevention of Adulterations and Non-Compliances in Organic and Geographical Indications Food Supply Chain – THEROS Project (Poster)	JSI	https://theros-project.eu/iso-food-24-26-04-2023/
23-25.05.2023	Innovate4Climate	Bilbao, Spain	Project video was showcased	NTTDATA	https://theros-project.eu/?p=1433&preview=true
22.06.2023	7th SCAR AE Meeting	Online	THEROS Project Overview	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/7th-scar-ae-meeting-22-06-2023/
26-30.06.2023	Data Spaces: Agriculture Data Week	Leipzig, Germany	AgriHub as Social Space for Agriculture Data	WRLS	https://theros-project.eu/?p=1460&preview=true
04.10.2023	Adaptation Futures 2023	Montreal, Canada	FOod REsilience Living Lab (FORELL): a proposed Soil-Food Living Lab linking soil health to food sustainability	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/adaptation-futures-2023-04-10-2023/

			and climate adaptation.		
08-09.04.2024	RSCy2024 Conference	Paphos, Cyprus	In Situ Soil Spectroscopy for Environmental Monitoring: Case Study in Western Greece Orange Orchards	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/rscy2024-conference-08-09-04-2024/
16-17.05.2023	ESRIN Agriculture Science Cluster Meeting	Frascati, Italy	THEROS Transparency and trust in organic food supply chain & GI products	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/esrin-agriculture-science-cluster-meeting-16-17-05-2024/
18-23.05.2024	91st International Agricultural Fair	Novisad, Serbia	THEROS Project Overview	OCS/ UNIVEREXPORT	https://theros-project.eu/91st-international-agricultural-fair-2024-18-23-05-2024/
27-28.09.2024	4th International Organic Fest	Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina	THEROS attended the event through its partner OCS, who participated in engaging discussions, sharing knowledge and experiences with colleagues in the field of organic production.	OCS	https://theros-project.eu/4th-international-organic-fest-27-28-09-2024/
07-08.10.2024	Biofest 2024	Subotica, Serbia	THEROS attended the event through its partner OCS, who participated in engaging discussions, sharing knowledge and experiences with colleagues in the field of organic production.	OCS	https://theros-project.eu/biofest-in-subotica-07-08-10-2024/
14-15.10.2024	Synergy Days 2024	Barcelona, Spain	Pitch An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/synergy-days-2024-14-15-10-2024/

			indications food supply chain + Presentation THEROS: An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain		
14-16.10.2024	FOODTECH congress	Novi Sad, Serbia	THEROS: An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain	OCS, SEAB, ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/foodtech-congress-14-16-10-2024/
18-20.10.2024	5th International Conference on Environmental Design and Health, ICED2024	Athens, Greece	Towards dynamic digital product passport: the approach for food sector	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/5th-international-conference-on-environmental-design-and-health-iced2024-18-20-10-2024/
05-08.11.2024	11th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Food Analysis	Prague, Czech Republic	Insights from THEROS and Data4Food2030 Research Projects	WRLS	https://theros-project.eu/11th-international-symposium-on-recent-advances-in-food-analysis-05-08-11-2024/
12-14.11.2024	38th EFFoST International Conference 2024	Bruges, Belgium	Real-Time Detection of Turmeric Adulteration with Metanil Yellow using a Miniaturized NIR Sensor and AI techniques	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/?p=2074&preview=true

12.11.2024	5-day training event (T3-Training week) for the ENTRUST project	Athens, Greece	Harnessing Advanced Agri-Data Tools: Transforming Organic & GI Supply Chains with THEROS	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/5-day-training-event-t3-training-week-for-the-entrust-project-12-11-2024/
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4.2 Workshops, Seminars, Webinars

The following Table 5 summarises THEROS attendance in related workshops/ webinars/ seminars during the first two years of the project duration.

Table 5 THEROS attended workshops/webinars/seminars between M01-M24

Date	Event	Participation (P) Organisation (O)	Workshop Theme	Involved partners	Website announcement
31.05.2023	Agriculture and Business: Opportunities for cooperation with the research community- Ημερίδα, με θέμα «Αγροδιατροφή και Επιχειρήσεις: Ευκαιρίες συνεργασίας με την ερευνητική κοινότητα»	(P)	Καινοτόμα εργαλεία ανάλυσης των ποιοτικών χαρακτηριστικών σε διάφορα στάδια της αγροδιατροφικής αλυσίδας” – “Innovative tools for the analysis of quality characteristics at various stages of the agro-food chain“	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%af%ce%b4%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%b5-%ce%b8%ce%ad%ce%bc%ce%b1-%ce%b1%ce%b3%cf%81%ce%bf%ce%b4%ce%b9%ce%b1%cf%84%cf%81%ce%bf%cf%86%ce%ae-%ce%ba%ce%b1%ce%b9-%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9/
13-16.05.2024	EO for Agriculture Under Pressure 2024 workshop	(P)	THEROS: An Integrated Toolbox Enhancing Verification in Food Supply Chains	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/eo-for-agriculture-under-pressure-2020-online-workshop-13-16-05-2024/
15.05.2024	Webinar: Tecnologías digitales aplicadas al mejillón	(P)	THEROS Project: The future of traceability in Europe	NTTDATA	https://theros-project.eu/webinar-tecnologias-digitales-aplicadas-al-mejillon-15-05-2024/
22.08.2024	THEROS workshop "Countryside under data fire" as	(O)	THEROS Project	WIRELESSI NFO, SUMAVA	https://theros-project.eu/theros-workshop-as-

	part of Země Živitelka agricultural exhibition				part-of-zeme-zivitelka-agricultural-exhibition-22-08-2024/
11.09.2024	Securing Our Food Supply Chains: EU's Innovative Initiatives to Combat Food Fraud, Improve Food Traceability and Sustainability, and Increase Consumers' Trust	(O) & (P)	Securing Our Food Supply Chains: EU's Innovative Initiatives to Combat Food Fraud, Improve Food Traceability and Sustainability, and Increase Consumers' Trust	THEROS project along with ALLIANCE, WATSON, FISHEUTRUST, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX	https://theros-project.eu/securing-our-food-supply-chains-webinar-series-11-13-09-2024/
13.09.2024					
04.10.2024	I3-4-BLUE-Growth Open Innovation Programme	(P)	Traceability technology for Aquaculture	NTTDATA	https://theros-project.eu/i3-4-blue-growth-open-innovation-programme-04-10-2024/
01.11.2024	Training on organic fruit and vegetable production, intended for young people from Bosnia and Herzegovina	(P)	Training on organic fruit and vegetable production, intended for young people from Bosnia and Herzegovina	OCS	https://theros-project.eu/agricultural-cluster-gls-and-the-network-of-young-agri-entrepreneurs-mma-01-11-2024/
14.11.2024	DPP and Traceability concept for organic foods	(P)	Digital Product Passport & Tracing (DPP)	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/?p=2063&preview=true

4.3 Exhibitions/Booths

The following Table 6 summarises THEROS attendance in related exhibitions/ booths during the first two years of the project duration.

Table 6 THEROS attended exhibition/booths between M01-M24

Date	Event	Exhibition (E)/ Booth (B)	Description	Involved partners	Description (if available)/url
18-23.05.2024	91st International Agricultural Fair	Booth	THEROS dissemination material was showcased in the OCS booth	OCS & Univerexport DOO	https://theros-project.eu/91st-international-agricultural-fair-2024-18-23-05-2024/
26-28.09.2024	2nd IEEE Conference on Agrifood	Booth	THEROS dissemination material was	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/2nd-ieee-conference-on-agrifood-

	Electronics (CAFE 2024)		showcased in the ICCS booth		electronics-cafe-2024-26-28-09-2024/
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4.4 Other activities

The following Table 7 summarises THEROS featuring in other activities during the first two years of the project duration.

Table 7 THEROS other activities between M01-M24

Date	Type of activity	URL
01/2023	THEROS on CORDIS EU page	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083579
12/2023	THEROS in Food 2030 Research & Innovation – Pathways for Action 2.0” policy report	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/new-report-food-2030-research-and-innovation-pathways-action-20-2023-12-04_en

4.5 Upcoming activities

THEROS recognizes the importance for the in advance planning of related activities, which are focused on advancing its research and dissemination efforts.

Towards this direction, THEROS participation has been already confirmed in the following event:

- NTTDATA internal event in May 2025.
- Workshop within the framework of the PoliRuralPlus Outreach Call project. (FARM TOURIST), on January 21st, 2025, at Klatovy CZ.
- Conference/workshop Open data week, Last week of January 2025, Prague, CZ.
- Workshop of the THEROS project within the framework of the international agricultural exhibition Země živitelka, August 2025, České Budějovice, CZ.

In addition, all THEROS team members will ensure that key results are disseminated through prominent events, conferences, workshops, seminars, webinars, exhibitions and booths.

All updates will be thoroughly reported in D6.3 “THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders’ engagement and liaison activities (final version)”, due in M36.

5. THEROS Clustering & Networking activities

THEROS pays particular attention to the establishment of key and mutually beneficial collaborations with sister and relevant projects, networks, bodies and initiatives. Thus, a dedicated task (Task 6.2) is coordinating such activities with the active and continuous support of Task 6.1 of communication and dissemination activities.

5.1 Catalogue of projects, bodies and initiatives

The THEROS project initially provided an indicative list of sister and related projects, as well as relevant EU bodies and initiatives, in D6.1: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholder Engagement, and Liaison Activities (Initial Version), delivered in M06. These lists have since been further refined and updated in M18, as part of D6.4: THEROS Knowledge Base (Initial Version) (Annexes 2 and 3). The enhancement of these lists will be an ongoing process, with the final, comprehensive versions set to be included in D6.5: THEROS Knowledge Base (Final Version) in M36.

5.2 THEROS Cluster

In February 2024, THEROS embarked on a transformative journey to revolutionize the European Union's food supply chains through innovation, sustainability, and consumer trust. This journey was the commencement of a cluster initiative which consisted of three flagship projects—THEROS, ALLIANCE, and WATSON—each designed to tackle critical challenges in food safety, traceability, and combating fraud.

As the initiative gained momentum, the cluster expanded to include five additional cutting-edge projects—FishEUtrust, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX, and TITAN. Together, this collaborative ecosystem of projects leverages advanced technology, multidisciplinary expertise, and policy-driven strategies to ensure the EU's food supply chains are not only secure but also resilient, transparent, and sustainable. The synergy among these eight projects fosters cross-disciplinary collaboration and accelerates the adoption of groundbreaking solutions. By addressing the multifaceted challenges facing modern food supply chains, this cluster is shaping a future where safety, sustainability, and trust go hand in hand.

In a significant milestone for the cluster, our first webinar—titled “Securing Our Food Supply Chains: EU's Innovative Initiatives to Combat Food Fraud, Improve Food Traceability and Sustainability, & Increase Consumer Trust” —was conducted successfully on 11th and 13th of September 2024 (Figure 12). This event showcased the collective vision and collaborative efforts of all projects.

Figure 12 Cluster webinar announcement banner

5.3 Cross fertilisation activities

Building on the content of the aforementioned lists, THEROS has actively participated in several mutually beneficial liaison activities throughout the first two years of the project. These efforts have fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange with various stakeholders. The following Table 8 provides a summary of THEROS's joint activities during this period.

Table 8 THEROS joint activities between M01-M24

Date	Type of activity	Event	Partners Involved	Related project	Website Announcement
13.02.2024	Kick off /Intro meeting	Kick-off Liaison meeting between THEROS, ALLIANCE and WATSON	ICCS, SEAB, JSI	ALLIANCE and WATSON	https://theros-project.eu/kick-off-liaison-meeting-between-theros-alliance-and-watson13-02-2024/
17.05.2024	2nd Progress meeting	2nd Progress meeting between THEROS, ALLIANCE and WATSON	ICCS, SEAB, JSI	ALLIANCE and WATSON	https://theros-project.eu/2nd-progress-meeting-between-theros-alliance-and-watson-17-05-2024/
16-17.05.2023	ESRIN Agriculture Science Cluster Meeting	ESRIN Agriculture Science Cluster Meeting	ICCS	CERBERUS, ScaleAgData, AgriDataValue, TEMBO AFRICA, SYLVA, EIFFEL, DINOSAR, WaterSense, AFRI4CAST,	https://theros-project.eu/esa-esrin-agriculture-science-cluster-meeting-16-17-05-2024/

				EOAfrica, WRM, HyRelief, CRISP, WorldCereal, ECOSTRESS HUB, YIPEEO, EO4NUTRI, EO4Cereal Stress	
15.05.2024	Webinar	Webinar: Tecnologías digitales aplicadas al mejillón	NTTDATA	EDIH DATAlife	https://theros-project.eu/webinar-tecnologias-digitales-aplicadas-al-mejillon-15-05-2024/
04.07.2024	Telco	Telco	ICCS, SEAB, JSI	FishEUtrust, SEAtosea, WATSON, ALLIANCE, CUES	https://theros-project.eu/kick-off-liaison-meeting-between-fisheustrust-seatosea-watson-alliance-cues-04-07-2024/
11.09.2024	Webinar	Securing Our Food Supply Chains: EU's Innovative Initiatives to Combat Food Fraud, Improve Food Traceability and Sustainability, and Increase Consumers' Trust	ICCS, SEAB	THEROS project along with ALLIANCE, WATSON, FISHEUTRUST, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX	https://theros-project.eu/securing-our-food-supply-chains-webinar-series-11-13-09-2024/
13.09.2024					
26-28.09.2024	Booth	2nd IEEE Conference on Agrifood Electronics (CAFE 2024)	ICCS	CiROCCO EU Project & DigiAfriFood	https://theros-project.eu/2nd-ieee-conference-on-agrifood-electronics-cafe-2024-26-28-09-2024/
14-15.10.2024	Workshop	Synergy Days 2024	ICCS	WATSON & FISHEUTRUST (+TITAN)	https://theros-project.eu/synergy-days-2024-14-15-10-2024/
14-16.10.2024	Conference	FOODTECH congress	OCS, SEAB, ICCS	ALLIANCE	https://theros-project.eu/foodtech-

					congress-14-16-10-2024/
12.11.2024	Conference	5-day training event (T3-Training week) for the ENTRUST project	ICCS	ENTRUST project	https://theros-project.eu/5-day-training-event-t3-training-week-for-the-entrust-project-12-11-2024/

5.4 Planned activities

THEROS has planned a series of collaborative activities with its sister projects to enhance synergies, foster knowledge exchange, and maximize the impact of shared efforts. These activities will include joint workshops, webinars, and collaborative research initiatives aimed at addressing common challenges and advancing the objectives of all involved projects. By aligning strategies and exchanging best practices, THEROS and its sister projects aim to create a more cohesive and integrated approach to achieving their respective goals. These planned interactions will strengthen the overall network, promote cross-project collaboration, and contribute to the broader success of related initiatives within the research and innovation landscape.

All activities will be thoroughly referenced within D6.5: THEROS Knowledge Base (Final Version) and D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version), in M36.

6. THEROS Ground Breakers Advisory Board

6.1 Interaction process

The THEROS Ground Breakers Advisory Board (GBAB) serves as a strategic advisory body, designed to ensure that the project aligns with industry needs, addresses real-world challenges, and disseminates impactful results to a broad audience. The GBAB's key functions include advising on project progress, contributing expert insights, and strengthening linkages with external stakeholders.

The GBAB focuses on:

- Identifying and addressing challenges and opportunities in the verification of organic and geographical indication (GI) food products.
- Providing expert feedback to refine the THEROS integrated toolbox and associated innovations.
- Strengthening synergies with related projects, initiatives, and networks.
- Disseminating project outcomes to amplify visibility and impact across relevant domains, including organic certification, food authenticity, and blockchain-enhanced traceability.

To ensure continuous and meaningful engagement, the GBAB interaction plan involves:

- *Periodic Meetings:* Scheduled at key project milestones, either virtual or in-person, to discuss progress, challenges, and next steps.
- *Deliverable Review Contributions:* Members are invited to provide comments and suggestions on critical deliverables, ensuring alignment with industry standards and stakeholder expectations.
- *Participation in Communication Activities:* The GBAB members contribute to THEROS dissemination efforts through webinars, interviews, and participation in newsletters and social media campaigns.
- *Involvement in Demonstration Activities:* Members are encouraged to provide hands-on feedback during pilot demonstrations to validate the tools and solutions in real-world scenarios.
- *Engagement through Events:* GBAB members attend THEROS-organized conferences, workshops, and networking events, promoting cross-fertilization with other EU-funded projects and initiatives.

As of M24, the following progress has been made regarding the GBAB:

Membership Development:

Confirmed participation of IFOAM (International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements), UCD School of Biosystems and Food Engineering (University College Dublin), and the JRC Directorate F – Health, Consumers, and Reference Materials Unit F.4 – Food Integrity.

Ongoing efforts to involve additional stakeholders, particularly those with expertise in food supply chain traceability and anti-fraud technologies.

Engagement Activities:

GBAB members have participated in discussions regarding the design and usability of the THEROS integrated toolbox. Received feedback has been also incorporated into the communication and dissemination strategy to improve the visibility of project outcomes among stakeholders.

Clustering Activities:

Collaborative efforts with the GBAB have facilitated knowledge exchange with other EU projects under HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01 and similar call topics.

6.2 Planning

Planned Activities

To enhance the effectiveness of the GBAB, the following activities are planned for the upcoming period (M25–M36).

Thematic Workshops: GBAB members will participate in thematic workshops to provide targeted feedback on:

- DNA-based authenticity tools for food fraud prevention.
- Blockchain-enabled traceability mechanisms.
- Green accountability tools for sustainability reporting.

Expanded Membership: Efforts will continue to onboard additional members from:

- National and EU regulatory bodies.
- Leading academic and research institutions focused on food quality and safety.
- Industry stakeholders, including SMEs and larger corporations, in organic food production and distribution.

Participation in Pilots and Validation Activities: GBAB members will be invited to observe and assess the results of pilot projects, ensuring practical applicability and relevance.

Final Report Contributions: The GBAB will contribute to the final project report, providing an external perspective on the project's achievements, challenges, and recommendations for future initiatives.

The GBAB is critical to the success and sustainability of the THEROS project, ensuring:

- Stakeholder Alignment: The solutions developed address real-world problems and meet stakeholder needs.
- Broader Dissemination: Project outcomes reach a wide audience, including policymakers, industry actors, and the general public.
- Knowledge Transfer: Expertise and insights from GBAB members enhance the project's outputs and ensure alignment with emerging trends and standards.

By fostering strong collaboration with the GBAB, the THEROS consortium is well-positioned to achieve its goal of modernizing the process of verifying organic and GI food products while preventing fraud and non-compliance.

7. Evaluation & monitoring of comm/diss activities

7.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Measurable communication and dissemination targets have been defined since the proposal stage to ensure the project achieves its intended impact. To facilitate the effective monitoring of these activities, a KPI (Key Performance Indicator) matrix has been developed in an Excel spreadsheet, which is regularly reviewed and updated on a monthly basis by the WP6 leader, SEAB. The KPI matrix is stored in the project's internal repository and tracks the names of the KPIs, their current values, and the expected outcomes by the project's completion. Figure 13 below shows the KPI matrix up to M24 (December 2024) for the THEROS project.

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION KPIs MATRIX		
KPIs Names	Current values (M24)	Threshold for the 3 rd year (M36)
Communication KPIs		
Website online: Unique visitors	2700	1500
Followers on Twitter & LinkedIn	383	500
Views on YouTube	877	200
e-Newsletters contributed/released	3	7
Total Mailing List Contact Points	70	200
Press activities	10	15
Factsheet	1	1
Standard presentation	1	1
Brochure	1	2
Poster	1	2
Roll up	1	2
Project official video	0	1
Pilot videos	0	4
Partners Interview series	12	17
Dissemination KPIs		
Publishing in Peer-reviewed Journals	0	5
Presenting in Scientific Conferences	27	20
Releasing Technical Publications	4	7
Focus Groups	0	4
Pilot demonstrations evaluation workshops	0	4
Final Event	0	1
Final event participants	0	100
EU events	1	2
Joint/Cluster activities with relevant Initiatives (no of projects)	30	10
Joint/Cluster activities with relevant Initiatives (no of activities)	11	N/A

Figure 13 THEROS KPIs monitoring matrix

7.2 Risk management and compliance

In THEROS, risk management plays a crucial role, especially within WP6. The project's complexity and the interdisciplinary nature of the consortium introduce various risk factors that could impact the successful implementation of the project. Table 9 below provides an updated overview of potential risks associated with THEROS WP6, specifically concerning Communication and Dissemination activities. It outlines the likelihood of each risk, its potential impact, and the mitigation strategies that have been put in place for each identified risk.

Table 9 THEROS WP6 risk registry

Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
<p>Low penetration and impact of THEROS brand name to the national and EU and audiences [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>THEROS team will proceed, at the early stages of the project, with: the development of a precise communication & dissemination strategy [M06], the design of the THEROS brand story [M02] and website [M01] and the creation of dedicated social media accounts [M02]. Statistics on the use of the THEROS webpage and social media accounts will be reviewed periodically to monitor visitors' flow and increase the diffusion in time.</p>
<p>Low engagement of consortium partners in dissemination/communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>Close collaboration of WP6 Leader with all consortium partners and continuous triggering of the inactive members through bi-lateral communication and regular WP6 meetings.</p>
<p>Conferences and relevant exhibitions/fairs may be cancelled or postponed [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>Follow closely any relevant opportunities and strive for virtual attendance.</p>
<p>Exploitation, dissemination & comm activities have a lower impact than expected [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>Regular monitoring of the success of dissemination and exploitation, activities, including through given KPIs, adjusting the strategy when necessary. To raise awareness on scope and results, high impact channels and Open Access publications will be used to maximize impact.</p>
<p>Confidential information is disclosed through project's dissemination/communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>THEROS has identified and described the required procedures for publishing project's dissemination and communication material since the early stages of the project via its CA. All partners are obliged to follow these guidelines. It has been also established a second level of security (procedures are detailed described in Annex 1), where all information related to communication/ dissemination issues must be first approved beforehand by THEROS Project Coordinator,</p>

	THEROS Technical Manager and the THEROS Communication Manager/WP6 Leader.
Difficulties in AB engagement, because of their internal turnover processes [Likelihood: Medium Severity: High]	Develop and maintain regular communication with the organizations that advisory board members represent to strengthen relationships and ensure alignment.
WP6 milestones or deliverables are delayed [Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium]	As part of project management activities, detailed analysis will be done on both global project and lower (WP/Task) project implementation levels. Thus, it will be ensured that cases that could delay any milestones or deliverables are recognised in advance, ensuring timely & effective implementation of necessary corrections in the work plan.
Losing critical staff or partners at crucial point of the project [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	Given the good reputation of all consortium partners, most of them with proven success records in H2020 Projects, this possibility is considered to be very unlikely. The General Assembly will decide whether the uncovered project activities can be carried-out by other partners. If not, then another partner would be recruited.
Overspending by one or more partners [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]	This situation will be detected early via management reports under T1.1. If this risk occurs, actions will be considered by the ExB, such as the escalation to the management of the affected partner(s) to mobilise more experienced or better skilled resources, capable of working more efficiently. Ad-hoc recovery plan will be put in place to reach the final targeted budget and requested funding.
Conflict to arise within the consortium [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	Continuous issue monitoring as well as the importance of ensuring continuous user and stakeholder commitment. Iterative process in the development and demos for issue management, addressing the issues of stakeholder complexity.
Snowball effects in case of delays due to unforeseen factors, e.g., a new pandemic wave [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	The consortium will employ all means for teleworking and remote collaboration. Therefore, the work in closed workspaces will be reduced to the minimum possible degree. For the cases that face-to-face meetings are unavoidable, the participants will conform with all the necessary healthcare precautions and necessary protocols.

8. Conclusions

This document provides a comprehensive summary of the communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and liaison activities conducted during the first two years of the THEROS project. It highlights the concerted efforts of the THEROS consortium partners to share the project's vision, results, progress, and key outcomes.

Consortium partners have actively participated in numerous events and created a variety of materials, including press releases, technical documents, and scientific publications. These efforts have been instrumental in raising awareness of the THEROS project and its advancements.

THEROS has fostered valuable collaborations and synergies with related projects, networks, and experts. These partnerships have been mutually beneficial, aiming to amplify the dissemination of THEROS outcomes and leverage shared expertise to enhance the project's impact.

THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version) is a dynamic, adaptable resource designed to refine and enrich the project's communication and engagement strategies. Its objective is to ensure the effective dissemination of information about the project's activities and results throughout its lifecycle and beyond. Regular updates will be incorporated into subsequent deliverables under Work Package 6 (WP6) and more specifically on D6.3 "THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version)" due in M36 and D6.5 "THEROS knowledge base (final version)", due in M30.

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- [3] EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms, available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary> (Last Access 27/12/2024).

Disclaimer of Warranties

'This project has used a standard methodology already developed in MOSES project (Grant Agreement number: 861678) and EVENTS project (Grant Agreement number: 101069614), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for THEROS (Grant Agreement number: 101083579).'